

PERFORMANCE OF LITHIUM-INTERCALATED CARBON FIBRES FOR STRUCTURAL ELECTRODE APPLICATIONS

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Keywords: *Carbon fibre, lithium intercalation, measured capacity, strength, expansion*

1 Introduction

Mass reduction is a priority for a wide range of systems that require structural components and electrical energy storage devices such as laptops or hybrid vehicles. Energy storage devices have high contribution to the system mass, as well as the mechanical structure. Thus, mass savings could be achieved with a structural battery, which consist of a multifunctional lightweight material able to simultaneously bear mechanical loads and store electrochemical energy. The carbon fibre (CF) has a high tensile strength and tensile stiffness-to-weight ratios and a graphitic microstructure which enables reversible lithium (Li)-ion intercalation reactions. The novel structural-battery concept can therefore rely on the use of CFs as structural electrodes in Li-ion battery.

Previous work has focused on the electrochemical performance of CFs used as electrodes. In Li-ion batteries, Li ions move through a porous separator impregnated with electrolyte from a negative to a positive electrode during charge (lithiation), and with a reverse flow during discharge (delithiation). The specific electrochemical energy storage capacity, which corresponds to the amount of intercalated-Li during a lithiation per unit weight, was investigated for a wide range of CF [1,2]. Polyacrylonitrile (PAN)-based CFs exhibited the best overall specific capacities which can be as good as ordinary graphite-based commercial electrode materials. However, the measured capacity of a CF tow depends on the electrochemical cycling rate (C-rate). For rates typically higher than 0.1C the diffusion of Li in the CF tow becomes rate limiting and the fibres are only partly lithiated. Other research work at 1C-rate [3] has shown that an external tensile force has no obvious impact on the measured specific capacity of PAN-based CF electrodes.

However, possible electrochemical effects on the mechanical performance of CFs remain unknown and of high interest for the modeling and development of CF structural electrodes. This paper investigates the deformation of the CF and the changes in the tensile properties induced by Li-intercalation and electrochemical cycling.

CF specimens were manufactured from a CF tow. Lithiated and delithiated specimens were subjected to tensile test after electrochemical cycling at 1C-rate to measure changes in the ultimate tensile strength (UTS) and the tensile stiffness with the number of electrochemical cycles [4]. A longitudinal expansion of the CF induced by Li-intercalation at about 7C, 1C and 0.1C-rate was measured [5] using mechanical tests and correlated with the measured capacity.

2 Material and methods

2.1 CF specimens and tensile test rig

The intermediate modulus PAN-based CF T800HB 6K 40B P1 BB 223tex sized (Torayca) was chosen for its good specific capacity in comparison with other fibres tested prior to this work by the authors [2]. The fiber exhibited a capacity of 136 mAh/g with a good retention after 10 cycles at 1C-charge rate.

Specimens made of CF tows were manufactured with 22 mm gauge length and end tabs which fit in the tensile stage of a microtester controlled with the Microtest software from Deben UK. The load cell was 300N which set a limit of about 4000 filaments per specimen, but commercial tows are not available in such a small size. Thus, a commercial tow with 24000 straight CF filaments was divided properly into lighter tows from which consistent tensile specimens were made. End tabs (12 mm long, 10 mm wide and about 1 mm thick)

were made from glass fibre composite laminae using a bonding technique which allowed good impregnation of the fibres in a stiff consistent and insulating tabbing fixture, as described in [3,4]. The specimens were dried at 50°C under reduced pressure for 24h and placed inside the glovebox prior to cell assembly. Fig. 1 shows a finished specimen [4].

The mass estimate of the CF specimens made from a same tow was obtained from weighing and was about 2.0 ± 0.1 mg (2630 ± 130 filaments). The consistency of the virgin specimens was checked with a series of tensile tests [4].

2.2 Glovebox and electrochemical cells

The CF specimens were used as electrodes in laboratory Li-ion half cells manufactured in a glovebox under inert argon atmosphere with less than 1 ppm [O₂] and [H₂O] at ambient temperature [3,4]. Fig. 2 presents a schematic side view of the cell assembly.

Each cell was made of one or several CF specimens used as electrode with a copper foil as current collector, a glass microfibre separator (Whatman GF/A) impregnated with 150µL 1.0 M LiPF₆ in EC:DEC (1:1 w/w, LP40 Merck) electrolyte, and a Li metal foil counter electrode with a nickel foil as current collector. The cell assembly was heat sealed inside a vacuum bag (Skultuna Flexible, PET / Al / PE, 12 µm / 9 µm / 75 µm thick) to ensure good contact between all layers and prevent the electrolyte from evaporating. The current collectors were connected to a Solartron 1286 Electrochemical Interface potentiostat controlled with the CorrWare software to run the electrochemical cycling of the cells.

Li metal has the lowest standard electrode potential and is therefore the negative electrode with the CFs as the positive electrode. Li metal is considered as an infinite source of Li which has a constant potential. Thus, any change in the cell potential is attributed to the potential of the CF electrode which depends on the concentration of Li in the fibers during cycling. Reaction (1) is the total redox reaction in the cell:

where x is an unknown parameter which depends on the chemical composition of the fiber. Each electrochemical cycle consisted of a galvanostatic lithiation, an open-circuit potential (OCP) that allows the cells to relax for 15 min, and a galvanostatic delithiation ending with another 15 min OCP. The current used for cycling was chosen according to the mass estimate of the fibre electrode in the cell and the desired cycling rate in mA/g. The fibres are considered completely charged at 0.002V vs. Li/Li⁺ during lithiations and completely discharged at 1.5V vs. Li/ Li⁺ during delithiations.

The measured specific capacity $C_s^{measured}$ is defined as the amount of electric charges received and delivered by the cell for lithiation and delithiation, respectively. It reflects the amount of intercalated Li in the CFs and is calculated with:

$$C_s^{measured} = I \times t / m \quad (2)$$

where I is the constant current applied (mA), t is the lithiation or delithiation duration (h) and m is the mass of the fiber electrode (g). A passivation layer about 10 nm thick, the solid-electrolyte interphase (SEI), caused by a decomposition of the electrolyte is formed during the first cycle at the surfaces of the CF electrode [6]. Some Li ions are used for the first lithiation to form the SEI layer and some other are irreversibly trapped in the CF microstructure. This process causes an irreversible first-cycle capacity loss which depends on the electrolyte formulation and on the specific surface area of the carbon electrode. For the next cycles the cells exhibit a capacity that can be considered as reversible between charge and discharge and with good retention.

2.3 Testing the relative changes in the tensile properties

The CF specimens being consistent, their cross-section area was considered as constant and the relative changes induced by Li intercalation on the CF modulus and UTS could be considered the same as on the tensile stiffness and ultimate tensile load of the specimens. For each CF specimen, the ultimate tensile load was measured on the tensile curve, as well as the ultimate tensile strain. The tensile stiffness of a CF specimen was defined herein as the slope of the tensile curve (force [N]) vs. (percent tensile strain [%]) where the deformation is linear elastic. It was calculated with the method of linear

least squares to fit data points, between load limits of about 400 mN/tex and 800 mN/tex as suggested for single filament [7].

Tensile tests were carried out in the glovebox on virgin specimens (before electrochemical cycling) and on lithiated and delithiated specimens collected after 1, 10, 100 and 1000 electrochemical cycles at about 1C-rate. For each of these numbers of cycle, the electrochemical cycling was carried out on two cells, each containing a sample of 3 to 4 specimens. When the target number of cycle was reached, one cell was stopped with a sample of delithiated specimens and the other one was run for an additional lithiation to have a sample of lithiated specimens. A slow motorspeed of 0.1 mm/min was used during tensile tests to keep a slow strain rate because of the small gauge length of the specimens.

For each sample of specimens cycled in a cell, a tensile property change was estimated with the normalized property according to:

$$P_n = \frac{P_{cycling}}{P_{virgin}} \pm \frac{\sigma}{P_{virgin}} \quad (3)$$

where P_n is the normalized sample property, $P_{cycling}$ and σ are the mean sample and the sample standard deviation, respectively. P_{virgin} is the mean property of the sample of virgin specimens.

2.4 Testing the longitudinal expansion

The longitudinal expansion of the CF can be measured with a specimen subjected simultaneously to a constant tensile strain and electrochemical cycling (Li-intercalation) because it will result in variations of the force carried by the specimen as illustrated in Fig. 3.

The longitudinal expansion can then be calculated from the variation of the tensile force ΔF and the tensile stiffness K of the CF specimen as in [3, 5]:

$$\varepsilon = \frac{\Delta F}{K} \quad (4)$$

For each cycling rate, the measurement was made with a cell containing a single CF specimen

electrode. The cell bag was clamped on the specimen end tabs inside the jaws of the microtester as presented in Fig. 4. Flat clamps were used to avoid puncturing the bag. A constant tensile extension was applied to the specimen and the bag which were pulled in parallel. The load relaxation in the bag was recorded for 3h until it stabilized and the electrochemical cycling of the cell was started.

Any variation of the tensile load carried by the CFs was measured during Li intercalation, and the measurement was repeated for several electrochemical cycles at about 7C, 1C, and 0.1C-rates. The tensile stiffness of the CF specimens were measured in subsequent tensile tests, after electrochemical cycling. The results of the measured expansion were correlated with the measured capacities and the tensile property changes to discuss the impact of the intercalated Li on the deformation and mechanical performance of the CFs.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Change in the tensile properties during electrochemical cycling

3.1.1 Measured capacity with the during electrochemical cycling

Fig. 5 presents the measured specific capacity for lithiation and delithiation at the 1st, 10th, 100th and 1000th electrochemical cycles at about 1C-rate [4]. The first-cycle capacity loss is seen in the capacity of the first delithiation which about half that of the first lithiation because some Li is irreversibly used in SEI layer formation. For the following cycles, the cells exhibited a good reversibility of the measured capacity with good retention. However, obvious losses in the capacity of the cells occurred continuously from about 200 cycles to 1000 cycles. Fewer and fewer Li was inserted in the fibres apparently because of the wear of the electrolyte and the Li metal electrode [4].

3.1.2 Change in the stiffness and UTS during electrochemical cycling

Fig. 6 shows the normalized tensile test curves of CF specimens after 10 electrochemical cycles [4] and Fig. 7 plots the normalized tensile stiffness and UTS of samples after 1, 10, 100 and 1000 electrochemical cycles.

Similar results were obtained after 1, 100 and 1000 cycles. The tensile curves show that the tensile stiffness of the specimens, reflected by the slopes of the curves where the deformation is linear elastic, remains unchanged with the number of cycles. Li intercalation seems to have no effect on the tensile modulus of CFs which is mainly related to the degree of orientation of the graphitic layer planes. About 9% losses were measured in the stiffness of after 1000 cycles and are attributed to premature wear of the screws of the tester clamp. They could also reflect a small impact of a long term-cycling on the orientation of the graphitic layers in the CF cross-section area.

The main impact of electrochemical cycling is seen in the changes of the UTS which drops during lithiation and partly recovers during delithiation [4]. By the first cycle the loss of UTS is ~20% in the lithiated CFs and partly recovered to only ~10%, in the delithiated CFs. The UTS drops when Li is inserted and recovers when Li is extracted again from the inner structure. Measurements at 10 and 100 cycles show that additional cycles up to 100 do not add any losses, which indicates that the first cycle is primarily responsible for the irreversible UTS loss in the delithiated fibres. However, after 1000 cycles the lithiated fibres exhibit a smaller UTS loss, closer to the one of delithiated fibres which remains the same (~10%) since the first cycle. These results suggest that the atomic microstructure of CFs and the strength of its interatomic bonds are conserved.

One possible explanation for the reversible drop of UTS could be that the inserted Li may create local stress concentrations leading to premature failure of the CFs. During delithiation, Li is removed from the fibre which may release internal stress and allow the recovery of strength. It is also important to highlight here that the losses measured in the UTS do not compromise the applicability of the CF as structural electrode.

3.1.3 Relation between the measured capacity and the change in the UTS

At the first cycle, irreversible Li-intercalation, which includes SEI formation, is responsible for a first-cycle irreversible capacity loss. A similar first-cycle irreversible UTS loss is measured. For the next cycles until 100 the measured capacity is reversible as well as the UTS loss. After 1000 cycles lower

losses were measured in the UTS of lithiated fibres (as seen on Fig 7), and the measured capacity during lithiation is also smaller. These comparisons suggest that the magnitude of the drops and recoveries in the UTS is governed by the measured capacity during electrochemical cycling, and may therefore directly depend on the amount of intercalated Li [4].

3.2 Longitudinal expansion of the CF induced by intercalated Li

3.2.1 Cycling rates and measured capacities during electrochemical cycling

The expansion of the CF was measured according to the method in 2.4. Table 1 reports the measurement during electrochemical cycling for each C-rates used, which is the fifth cycle at 7C and 1C and the third cycle at 0.1C.

The first-cycle capacity loss is smaller for the highest rates (7C) and tends to stabilize for the lowest rates (1C and 0.1C). From the second cycle the capacity can be considered as reversible between lithiations and delithiations with a good retention with the number of cycles. Efficiencies slightly higher than 100 % at low rate (0.1C) are not commonly seen in these tests, but may occasionally happen and are attributed to flat electrode potential curves at low C-rates affecting the termination of the charging cycle. The results at the last cycle show as in [2,5] that the lower the charge rate, the higher the charge time and the measured capacity which at 0.1C is close to the saturated value of Li storage in pure graphite (372mAh/g).

3.2.2 Measurement of the longitudinal expansion

Fig. 8 shows the variation of the force carried by CF specimens subjected to a constant extension during cycling at about 7C, 1C and 0.1C-rates. The green curve with square markers represents the load relaxation in the bag only when no fibres are loaded. For each cycling rate a CF specimen is loaded. The force relaxation in the bag is measured for the first 3h and the electrochemical cycling is started. The force drops during lithiation, is unchanged during OCP and increases during delithiation. The tensile stiffness is not affected by Li-intercalation, as shown in 3.1. Thus, the variation of the force indicates an expansion and contraction of the CF during lithiation and delithiation, respectively, as described in 2.4. There is an obvious first-cycle irreversible

expansion measured in the delithiated CFs because the force drop for the first lithiation is larger than the increase of the force measured for the first delithiation. For the next cycles the longitudinal expansion can be considered as reversible.

Fig. 9 presents the longitudinal expansion of T800H CFs as function of the capacity measured during the last lithiation at the different C-rates [5]. The figure plots the continuous expansion during the last lithiation at different C-rates indicated with different markers at the end of the lithiation. A dash-dot line connects the markers and shows the total expansion of the lithiated CFs. The same markers are for the same C-rates on a dashed line to indicate the irreversible expansion in the delithiated CFs after the last cycle. The last cycle-reversible expansion is seen in the difference between the dash-dot line and the dashed line at the different C-rates. The total expansion of the lithiated CFs, which is the sum of the irreversible expansion of delithiated fibres and the reversible expansion during lithiation, increases with lower C-rates. At 0.1C-rate, the capacity is close to 372mAh/g and the expansion is the highest, about 1.05 % [5].

The expansion increases with the amount of intercalated Li during lithiation. The C-rate has also an impact on the expansion, mainly because irreversible expansion in the delithiated CFs increases with lower C-rates, suggesting that more Li is trapped in the delithiated CFs. Thus, the first-cycle irreversible capacity not only relates to SEI formation, but also to irreversibly intercalated Li. More research needs to be done on the diffusion of Li in the electrolyte and within CF tows for a better understanding of the effects of the C-rate.

However, the longitudinal expansion seems to correspond to an elastic deformation induced by intercalated Li acting as a tensile load. Thus, the fibres might be pre-stressed in tension after electrochemical cycling which explains the UTS loss measured in the tensile tests in 3.1.

4 Conclusion

It was shown that during lithiation, the CFs expand in the longitudinal direction and their UTS drops. During delithiation, some strength is recovered and the CFs contract. The loss of UTS seems to depend on the measured capacity. The expansion of the CF is clearly governed by the measured capacity. These

results suggest that the intercalated Li creates tensile strain in the CF which is pre-stressed in tension and exhibit lower UTS in tensile tests.

Acknowledgements

Funding by the Swedish Foundation for Strategic Research (SSF), framework grant RMA08-0002, and from the Swedish Research Council, project 621-2012-3764, is gratefully acknowledged. The authors would like to thank Gurit, Toho Tenax, Soficar and Deben UK for material and helpful discussions. The Swedish research group Kombatt is also gratefully acknowledged for its guidance.

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Tables

C-rate [mAh/g]	Charge time [h]	1 st -cycle capacity loss [mAh/g]	Last cycle capacity ^a [mAh/g]	
			L	D
6.91C (940)	0.06	56	56	56
0.94C (128)	1.27	174	163	160
0.11C (15)	24.43	154	354	369

^aL is for lithiation and D is for delithiation.

Table 1. Cell capacity measurement at different cycling rates.

Figures

Fig. 1. IMS65 CF tensile specimen with the end tabs and dimensions.

Fig. 2. Schematic side view of a laboratory electrochemical cell.

Fig. 3. Schematic of a test of the CF longitudinal expansion induced by intercalated Li.

Fig. 4. Cell bag containing a CF specimen clamped in the microtester during electrochemical cycling.

Fig. 5. Measured capacity at after a number of electrochemical cycles.

Fig. 6. Normalized tensile curves after 10 electrochemical cycles.

Fig. 7. Measured capacity at after a number of electrochemical cycles.

Fig. 8. Tensile force carried by CF specimens under constant extension for electrochemical cycling.

Fig. 9. Longitudinal expansion of T800H CFs with the measured capacity for the last lithiation at different C-rates.